

Projective measurements can probe nonclassical work extraction and time correlations

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Quantum correlation functions are a natural way to encode multitime information, as they are ubiquitous in analysis from fluctuation theorems to information scrambling. Correlation functions can be identified with quasiprobabilities associated to quantum processes. In this work we show how these can be measured via error-cancellation techniques, using projective measurements only and no ancillae. The scheme is implemented in a nitrogen-vacancy center in diamond undergoing a unitary quantum work protocol. We reconstruct quantum-mechanical time correlations encoded in the Margenau-Hills quasiprobabilities by observing work extraction peaks five times those of sequential projective energy measurement schemes and in violation of newly derived stochastic bounds. We interpret the phenomenon via anomalous energy exchanges due to the underlying negativity of the quasiprobability distribution.

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I. INTRODUCTION

There is no unique way of defining a joint probability for the multitime statistics of quantum mechanical quantities, since even a single quantum observable does not always commute with itself at different times, leading to information-disturbance trade-offs. Nevertheless, across the quantum sciences, multitime fluctuations of quantum-mechanical quantities, especially energy, play a crucial role. For example, the celebrated fluctuation theorems in nonequilibrium thermodynamics characterize the statistics of the energy difference between an initial and a final time [1].

A natural way to characterize quantum-mechanical fluctuations is via correlation functions. Correlation functions between events at different times resemble joint probability distributions for the eigenvalues of the observables, but they

are in general neither real nor positive. In fact, they are represented by *quasiprobabilities*, akin to the well-known Wigner function in quantum optics [2] but associated with a *process* rather than a state. The standard definition of a temporal correlation function between two events described by projectors $\Pi_i(0)$ and $\Pi_f(t)$ is [3,4]

$$q_{if}^{\text{KD}} = \text{Tr}[\rho \Pi_i(0) \Pi_f(t)], \quad (1)$$

which *coincides* with the Kirkwood-Dirac quasiprobability (KDQ) [5–7], and the same goes for multitime extensions. It is also standard to consider the symmetrized correlation function $q_{if} = \text{Re } q_{if}^{\text{KD}}$, which *coincides* with the Margenau-Hill quasiprobability (MHQ) [8]. While quantum correlation functions are a well-known toolkit in quantum-mechanical analysis, their identification with the KDQ and MHQ has recently led to identify their centrality in a variety of new scenarios [7,9–16], as well as to the development of new measurement techniques, as surveyed in Ref. [17].

In terms of applications, these quasiprobabilities have been used for state characterization [18] and to underpin information scrambling analysis [19,20]. Weak values [21,22] are conditional KDQs [17,20], and generalized *anomalous weak values* [21,22] are in one-to-one correspondence with negative or complex KDQs [23,24]. The latter are themselves related to forms of nonclassicality in appropriate operational scenarios [25] via contextuality [24,26,27] and in connection with Leggett-Garg inequality violations [28–30]. Moreover,

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negative values of the MHQ are linked to quantum metrological advantages in both local and postselected setups [12,27,31] and to power output advantages in quantum thermodynamics [27].

In terms of measurement schemes, through their link to weak values, the KDQ and MHQ are traditionally measured via weak measurements, which involve a weak interaction with an ancillary system [21,32,33]. The need to collect a large amount of data to overcome statistical noise and the need for small back-reactions are challenges faced by this scheme [34]. It was later understood theoretically, and proved experimentally, that the need for a weak interaction for wave-function reconstruction and weak values can be lifted [35–37], and the idea was recently extended to out-of-order-correlations for qubit systems under certain restrictions [34].

In this work, we demonstrate that we can also lift the need for controlled interactions with auxiliary measurement ancillae by providing the first experimental demonstration of a *weak two-point measurement* (wTPM) scheme measuring quantum time correlators [17,38]. We achieve the *back-reaction-free limit*, encapsulated in quasiprobabilities, by linearly combining different projective measurement schemes in such a way that back-reactions cancel. Conceptually, our idea can be seen as a twist on probabilistic error cancellation techniques in quantum computing where an ideal error-free limit is inferred by sampling noisy circuits [39,40].

We also employ these new techniques to investigate *nonclassical energetic processes*. The study of this kind of processes is swiftly transitioning from theory to experimental implementations [41,42]. It has been shown experimentally [43] and theoretically [44,45] that nonclassical effects deteriorate as the measurement strength increases. The issue that measurement disturbance destroys quantum thermodynamic effects has been the subject to a long-standing debate, e.g., see Refs. [10,17,46,47]. Using the wTPM scheme we bypass this issue, and we experimentally reconstruct the work distribution function based on the MHQ, hence accessing genuinely nonclassical thermodynamic effects, with strong (projective) measurements only and no ancillae. In addition, we derive and show experimentally the violation of corresponding stochastic work bounds, in the presence of negative values of the MHQ. Specifically, in a driven three-level system, the measured average work extraction peaks are up to 5 times those achieved using the standard two-point-projective measurement (TPM) scheme [48]. We explain this phenomenon by interpreting negative probabilities as nonclassical pathways of a stochastic process.

II. NONCLASSICALITY AND WORK INEQUALITIES

The KDQ encodes temporal correlations between quantum observables and so does its real part, the MHQ. Here we focus on the latter. Consider two observables $A(0) \equiv \sum_i a_i \Pi_i(0)$ and $B(t) \equiv \sum_f b_f \Xi_f(t)$ in terms of their eigenvalues a_i, b_f and their eigenprojectors $\Pi_i(0), \Xi_f(t)$, and a quantum channel \mathcal{E} describing the system dynamics in the time interval $[0, t]$. The MHQ reads as

$$q_{if}(\rho, t) = \text{Re Tr}[\rho \Pi_i(0) \mathcal{E}^\dagger(\Xi_f(t))], \quad (2)$$

where \mathcal{E}^\dagger denotes the adjoint of \mathcal{E} and ρ is the quantum state at $t = 0$. The MHQ is a *quasiprobability*, as it is linear in ρ and satisfies $\sum_{i,f} q_{if} = 1$ with $q_{if} \in \mathbb{R}$ but not necessarily ≥ 0 . The nonclassicality of the MHQ is defined via *the negativity functional* [7,17,49]

$$\aleph \equiv -1 + \sum_{i,f} |q_{if}(\rho, t)|. \quad (3)$$

The marginals of a MHQ, over i (f) reproduce the expected outcome statistics of a measurement of $B(t)$ at time t ($A(0)$ at time 0). Finally, being a two-time correlator [50], the MHQ encodes information about the *process*, including its linear response and quantum currents [17,51].

In our experiments $A(0)$ and $B(t)$ are the Hamiltonian at times 0 and t and the channel is a unitary work protocol U , i.e., $\mathcal{E}(\cdot) \equiv \mathcal{U}(\cdot) \equiv U(\cdot)U^\dagger$. The “unperturbed” work $\langle w \rangle_t \equiv \text{Tr}[H(t)\rho(t)] - \text{Tr}[H(0)\rho(0)]$ can be obtained as the average

$$\langle w \rangle_t \equiv \text{Tr}[H(t)\rho(t)] - \text{Tr}[H(0)\rho(0)] = \sum_{i,f} q_{if}(\rho, t) w_{if} \quad (4)$$

with $w_{if} \equiv E_f(t) - E_i(0)$. Clearly, the same framework applies to the study of temporal correlations beyond work processes.

The quantum process has a stochastic (classical) interpretation when $q_{if} \geq 0$ for all i, f . In fact, for fixed i, f , commutativity implies positivity: If (a) $[\rho, \Pi_i] = 0$ or (b) $[\Pi_i, \mathcal{E}^\dagger(\Xi_f)] = 0$ or (c) $[\mathcal{E}^\dagger(\Xi_f), \rho] = 0$, then $q_{if} \geq 0$ [17]. The converse does not hold, i.e., negativity is a *stronger* property than noncommutativity [7]. In cases (a) and (b), q_{if} reduces to the TPM probability of observing outcomes i followed by f in a sequential projective measurement of the observables $A(0)$ and $B(t)$, including the intermediate evolution \mathcal{E} .

Negative values of q_{if} indicate nonclassicality in the temporal correlations. In fact, these are associated with proofs of contextuality [24,26] and correspond to elementary nonclassical processes. For work protocols, crucially an *anomalous excitation process* $E_f > E_i$ (classically associated to work done, not extracted) occurring with “negative probability” $q_{if} < 0$ is equivalent to a *classical deexcitation* process occurring with probability $|q_{if}|$, and hence it contributes to the extracted work.

For work extraction from *pure states*, we can derive an upper bound on the extractable work W_{ext} that holds whenever a stochastic interpretation is possible, i.e., $\aleph = 0$. Let us consider the case entailed by our experiment with a unitary work protocol U , an initial pure state $|\xi\rangle$, and rank-1 projectors on the initial and final energy eigenstates, i.e., $\Pi_i = |E_i(0)\rangle\langle E_i(0)|$ and $\Xi_f = |E_f(t)\rangle\langle E_f(t)|$. The MHQ is thus given by

$$q_{if} = \text{Re} \langle \xi | E_i(0) \rangle \langle E_i(0) | U^\dagger | E_f(t) \rangle \langle E_f(t) | U | \xi \rangle, \quad (5)$$

where

$$\langle \xi | E_i(0) \rangle = e^{-i\Phi_i^{(I)}} \sqrt{p_i}, \quad (6)$$

$$\langle E_i(0) | U^\dagger | E_f(t) \rangle = e^{-i\Phi_{if}^{(C)}} \sqrt{p(f|i)}, \quad (7)$$

$$\langle E_f(t) | U | \xi \rangle = e^{-i\Phi_f^{(E)}} \sqrt{p_f^{\text{END}}}. \quad (8)$$

In Eqs. (6)–(8), $p_i \equiv |\langle E_i(0) | \xi \rangle|^2$ are the initial probabilities, $p(f|i) \equiv |\langle E_f(t) | U | E_i(0) \rangle|^2$ denote the conditional probabilities of observing the outcome $E_f(t)$ in the final projective measurement conditioned on having $|E_i(0)\rangle$ as the initial state, and $p_f^{\text{END}} \equiv |\langle E_f(t) | U | \xi \rangle|^2$ are the probabilities of the end-point measurement protocol [52–54]. Thus, noticing that the TPM scheme probabilities are given by $p_{if}^{\text{TPM}} \equiv p_i p(f|i)$, we end up with

$$q_{if} = A_{if} \sqrt{p_{if}^{\text{TPM}} p_f^{\text{END}}}, \quad (9)$$

where we have defined $A_{if} \equiv \cos(\Phi_i^{(I)} + \Phi_{if}^{(C)} + \Phi_f^{(E)}) \in [-1, 1]$. From Eq. (9) one can see that the MHQ can be larger or smaller than their TPM counterpart depending on the end-point probabilities and the *activities* A_{if} . The latter encodes quantum interference and, indeed, $q_{if} \geq 0 \iff A_{if} \geq 0$. Now let us assume that the probabilities of the TPM and end-point schemes are fixed, and we introduce the extractable (when positive) work that is defined as

$$W_{\text{ext}} \equiv -\langle w \rangle_t = \langle \xi | H(0) | \xi \rangle - \langle \xi | U^\dagger H(t) U | \xi \rangle \quad (10)$$

that is just the average energy change, since the process is unitary. Hence, we see immediately that, if $A_{if} \geq 0 \forall i, f$, then

$$W_{\text{ext}} \leq - \sum_{i,f \text{ s.t. } w_{if} < 0} w_{if} \sqrt{p_{if}^{\text{TPM}} p_f^{\text{END}}} \quad (11)$$

that gives an upper bound to the work extraction when $\aleph = 0$. An analogous bound can be found when considering the absorbed work W_{abs} :

$$W_{\text{abs}} \equiv \langle w \rangle_t \leq \sum_{i,f \text{ s.t. } w_{if} > 0} w_{if} \sqrt{p_{if}^{\text{TPM}} p_f^{\text{END}}}, \quad (12)$$

when $\aleph = 0$.

Three experiments are needed to verify a violation of the inequality (11): (i) the characterization of the initial average energy; (ii) projective measurements of the energy at the beginning and end of the protocol, i.e., performing the TPM scheme; (iii) the projective measurement of the energy only at the end of the protocol, i.e., performing the end-point measurement protocol. (i) and (iii) are the standard ways to assess changes in the expectation values of observables in quantum mechanics and they allow us to estimate the left-hand side of Eq. (11). Instead, the second measurement serves the purpose of comparing with a scenario involving *measurement disturbance* and allows the computation of the right-hand side of the bound. Equation (11) is one of the main results of the paper. A violation of this bound (or the analogous one for the absorbed work) is a witness of nonclassicality of the dynamical process of work. This witness is not required to reconstruct the entire MHQ distribution but only perform projective measurements that are routinely carried out.

Finally, standard TPM experiments satisfy these inequalities. Hence, their violations indicate work extraction peaks above TPM that can only occur because negativity is at play. We will look for these peaks in the experimental data by optimizing the negativity of anomalous excitation processes within the experimentally achievable parameters.

III. MEASUREMENT PROCEDURE TO ACCESS MHQ

Next we present an experimental implementation of the wTPM measurement scheme [38] for the reconstruction of q_{if} . The latter is a *nonselective* (NS) 2-outcome projective measurement that checks whether the initial energy is E_i or NOT E_i , followed by a unitary evolution and a projective measurement of the final Hamiltonian. The wTPM joint probabilities read as

$$p_{if}^{\text{wTPM}} \equiv \text{Tr}[\mathcal{U}(\rho_{\text{NS},i}) \Xi_f(t)], \quad (13)$$

where $\rho_{\text{NS},i} \equiv p_i \rho_i + (1 - p_i) \bar{\rho}_i$, with $\rho_i \equiv \Pi_i \rho \Pi_i / p_i$ and $\bar{\rho}_i \equiv (\mathbb{I} - \Pi_i) \rho (\mathbb{I} - \Pi_i) / (1 - p_i)$. The state $\rho_{\text{NS},i}$ can be obtained by performing nonselective projective measurements with projectors Π_i and $\mathbb{I} - \Pi_i$ or, equivalently, by the preparation of the states ρ_i and $\bar{\rho}_i$ with the corresponding probabilities (as in our experiments). The joint probability (13) is related to the MHQ [17,38] via the relation

$$q_{if} = p_{if}^{\text{TPM}} - \frac{1}{2}(p_{if}^{\text{wTPM}} - p_f^{\text{END}}). \quad (14)$$

This entails that the MHQ is given by three distinct contributions [55], which stem from applying in three separate sets of runs the wTPM protocol, and the TPM and END schemes, respectively.

The combination of projective measurement schemes is analogous, in spirit, to “probabilistic error cancellation” [39], as commented in the introduction. Indeed, by algebraically combining the three disturbing measurements we reconstruct the unperturbed process as captured by the MHQ, which recovers the unperturbed average work accounting for the initial quantum coherence among distinct energies. Thus, our scheme can be understood as an error mitigation technique applied to quantum thermodynamics. The operator equality allowing operating this cancellation procedure is

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2}(\Pi_i \rho + \rho \Pi_i) \\ &= \Pi_i \rho \Pi_i - \frac{1}{2}[(\mathbb{I} - \Pi_i) \rho (\mathbb{I} - \Pi_i) + \Pi_i \rho \Pi_i] + \frac{\rho}{2}, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

from which Eq. (14) can be derived. Each term on the right-hand-side of Eq. (15) can be associated with a different projective measurement scheme.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In our experiments, the quantum system we use is the electronic spin of an NV center in bulk diamond at room temperature. NV centers are defects in a diamond lattice with an orbital ground state that is a spin triplet $S = 1$. The degeneracy in the spin quantum number m_S is lifted due to the zero field splitting and to the presence of an external bias field aligned with the spin quantization axis. The NV spin qutrit can be optically initialized into $m_S = 0$ ($|0\rangle$), by illuminating the defect with a green laser [56]. Moreover, the spin state can be read out by detecting the photoluminescence (PL) after a laser illumination, as the PL intensity depends on the spin projection m_S [57,58]. In addition, on-resonance microwave fields are used to coherently drive the spin, with coherence times up to milliseconds (at room temperature) [59,60]. By virtue of these properties, NV centers are broadly used for quantum

FIG. 1. Energy diagram for the NV center spin triplet: (a) in the laboratory frame according to the Hamiltonian $\mathcal{H}(t)$ in Eq. (17); (b) in the mw rotating frame, as described by the Hamiltonian $H(t)$ in Eq. (18); (c) in a rotating frame where the Hamiltonian is effectively time independent. Equation (17), indeed, can be transformed in the rotating frame determined by the unitary transformation $V = \exp[jt((\omega_{+1} + \phi_1)|+1\rangle\langle+1| + (\omega_{-1} + \phi_2)|-1\rangle\langle-1|)]$ where, after the rotating wave approximation, the time-independent Hamiltonian is $\tilde{H} = \Omega_1 S_{x1} - \phi_1 S_{z1} + \Omega_2 S_{x2} + \phi_2 S_{z2}$ with $S_{z1} = |+1\rangle\langle+1|$ and $S_{z2} = |-1\rangle\langle-1|$. Such a diagram represents a stimulated Raman adiabatic passage (STIRAP) experiment for a three-level ladder scheme [70]. It is worth noting that in the rotating frame (c), the time-varying phase of each mw field can be reinterpreted as detuning.

technologies, such as quantum sensing [61–63], quantum information [64,65], and, recently, for quantum thermodynamics [66–69].

The three-level system realized for our experiments is based on the spin-triplet $S = 1$ of the orbital ground state of an NV center with Hamiltonian

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{NV}} = \Delta S_z^2 + \gamma_e B S_z, \quad (16)$$

where $\Delta = 2.87$ GHz is the zero-field-splitting, γ_e denotes the electron gyromagnetic ratio, and B is a bias magnetic field aligned with the NV quantization axis z (determined by the orientation of the NV defect in the diamond lattice). A time-varying Hamiltonian is implemented by coherently driving the NV spin with a microwave (mw) field with the phase changing in time. Specifically, the spin qutrit is driven by a bichromatic microwave field that is on-resonance with both the transitions $|0\rangle \leftrightarrow |-1\rangle$ and $|0\rangle \leftrightarrow |+1\rangle$. Hence, overall the spin dynamics is described by the Hamiltonian

$$\mathcal{H}(t) = \mathcal{H}_{\text{NV}} + \{\Omega_1 \cos[\omega_{+1}t + \phi_1(t)] |+1\rangle\langle 0| + \Omega_2 \cos[\omega_{-1}t + \phi_2(t)] |-1\rangle\langle 0| + \text{H.c.}\}, \quad (17)$$

where $\hbar = 1$ and Ω_1, Ω_2 are the Rabi frequencies for the transitions $|0\rangle \leftrightarrow |+1\rangle$ and $|0\rangle \leftrightarrow |-1\rangle$, respectively. In addition, $\omega_{\pm 1} \equiv \Delta \pm \gamma_e B$ denote the frequencies, and $\phi_1(t)$ and $\phi_2(t)$ the time-varying phases of the mw fields. The energy level structure of the qutrit and its interaction with the mw fields is depicted in Fig. 1(a).

In the microwave rotating frame, the Hamiltonian of the system (after the rotating wave approximation) is

$$H(t) = \Omega_1 (S_{x1} \cos \phi_1 t + S_{y1} \sin \phi_1 t) + \Omega_2 (S_{x2} \cos \phi_2 t - S_{y2} \sin \phi_2 t), \quad (18)$$

where S_α are the spin operators defined in terms of the Gell-Mann matrices, i.e., $S_{x1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\lambda_1$, $S_{y1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\lambda_2$, $S_{x2} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\lambda_6$,

and $S_{y2} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\lambda_7$, with the Gell-Mann matrices given by

$$\lambda_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\lambda_6 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda_7 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & i & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

In accordance with our experiments, in Eq. (18) we selected the time-varying phases so that they change linearly in time, i.e., $\phi_1(t) = \phi_1 t$ and $\phi_2(t) = -\phi_2 t$. The energy level structure in the mw rotating frame is sketched in Fig. 1(b).

V. WORK QUASIPROBABILITIES

The MHQ plays a role in thermodynamics, where the characterization of work, heat, and internal energy fluctuations in quantum processes calls for novel tools to account for exquisitely quantum effects. The seminal TPM scheme [48,71,72] is unable to capture noncommutativity [10]. This motivated the use of the MHQ to characterize nonclassical work fluctuations [9] and anomalous heat exchanges due to quantum correlations [11]. However, experimental realizations remained limited, due to the challenge of adapting TPM experiments to access work quasiprobabilities. Here we experimentally reconstruct the MH work quasiprobability on the NV center using only projective energy measurements and pure state preparations. The latter feature paves the way for performing similar experiments with systems already analyzed with the TPM scheme.

We take the initial state to be pure $\rho = |\xi\rangle\langle\xi|$. The state $|\xi\rangle$ is chosen over an ensemble of 1000 initial pure random states as the state that *minimizes* q_{-+} , associated to the positive work realization $E_+ - E_-$, when considering the Hamiltonian (18) with $\Omega \simeq (2\pi)2.2$ MHz and $\phi \simeq 1.09\Omega$. This results in $|\xi\rangle \equiv \sum_i \sqrt{p_i} e^{2\pi j a_i} |E_i(0)\rangle$, with $j^2 = -1$, $p_i = 0.7654, 0.0009, 0.2338$ and $a_i = 0.0073, 0.2787, 0.0002$ for $i = +, 0, -$ respectively. With our experimental platform, we then reconstruct the single-time and joint probabilities p_f^{END} , p_{if}^{TPM} , and p_{if}^{wTPM} , by measuring a set of conditional probabilities of the form

$$p(f|\psi) \equiv \text{Tr}[\mathcal{U}(|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|)\Xi_f(t)], \quad (19)$$

where $|\psi\rangle$ depends on the scheme that we want to implement, as detailed in Fig. 2(a). We directly measure $p_f^{\text{END}} = p(f|\xi)$ for the END scheme. Instead, for the TPM and wTPM schemes we measure the conditional probabilities $p(f|i)$ and $p(f|\bar{i})$ by initializing the quantum states ρ_i and $\bar{\rho}_i$, respectively, and we combine them as $p_{if}^{\text{TPM}} = p_i p(f|i)$ and $p_{if}^{\text{wTPM}} = p_i p(f|i) + (1 - p_i) p(f|\bar{i})$ (we recall $p_i = \text{Tr}[\rho \Pi_i]$).

The protocol to measure these conditional probabilities is based on our previous works [67–69]. The measurement of $p(f|\psi)$ for each of the different initial states $|\xi\rangle, |i\rangle$, and $|\bar{i}\rangle$ is convenient in our experimental setup, where we follow the protocol described in Figs. 2(b) and 2(c). Specifically, the qutrit is initially prepared in the pure state $|\psi\rangle \in \{|\xi\rangle, |i\rangle, |\bar{i}\rangle\}$. For such a preparation, we initialize the system into $|0\rangle$ and

we apply the mw gate \mathcal{R}_i such that $\mathcal{R}_i(|0\rangle\langle 0|) = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$. Note that this is possible since $|\psi\rangle$ is a pure state for any of the schemes. The qutrit then evolves unitarily under the Hamiltonian in Eq. (18) for a time t . During this unitary evolution, the quantum system exchanges work with the microwave field. Finally, we measure the probability that the energy of the system is $E_f(t)$, i.e., we read out $p(f|\psi)$. In order to achieve the final energy measurement, we apply a microwave gate \mathcal{R}_f to the quantum system, such that $\mathcal{R}_f(\Xi_f) = |0\rangle\langle 0|$, and then we measure the PL intensity.

As mentioned, the PL intensity (averaged over $\sim 10^6$ repetitions of the experiment to overcome the low photon collection efficacy and shot noise of the detector) encodes information about the spin state, and it depends on the spin projection m_s . Hence, we normalize it with respect to the PL reference levels to obtain the probability for the qutrit to be in the state $|0\rangle$: $\text{Tr}[\mathcal{R}_f(\mathcal{U}(|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|))|0\rangle\langle 0|] = \text{Tr}[\mathcal{U}(|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|)\mathcal{R}_f^{-1}(|0\rangle\langle 0|)] = p(f|\psi)$. Note that the eigenstates of the Hamiltonian change in time, and hence the gate \mathcal{R}_f depends on the final time t . For a given initial state we perform independent experiments, given that the optical read-out is destructive for several values of t and for each of the three Hamiltonian projectors $\Xi_f(t)$.

FIG. 3. Experimental results from the END scheme [panel (a)], and from the measurements of the conditional probabilities obtained by initializing the qutrit in the states ρ_i [panels (b)] and $\bar{\rho}_i$ [panels (c)]. The solid lines denote the simulations using Eq. (18) with $\Omega = (2\pi)2.219$ MHz and $\phi = 1.09\Omega$. Note that the data for $f = 0$ are always constant. This is a consequence of setting $\phi_1 = \phi_2 = \phi$. In such a case, the interaction between the NV center and the two microwave fields corresponds to STIRAP in the two-photon resonance condition [70]. The data outside the interval $[0,1]$ is originated by photon shot noise during the PL read-out, hence affecting the PL normalization.

The results for the measurements of p_f^{END} , $p(f|i)$, and $p(f|\bar{i})$ are shown in Fig. 3. Moreover, the MHQ work distributions at each t is obtained by combining the results of all the performed measurements, as dictated by Eq. (14), see Figs. 4(a)–4(c). From Eq. (3), the nonclassicality is quantified by the negativity of the measured work distribution. Its experimental values are plotted in Fig. 4(d).

VI. ANOMALOUS WORK EXTRACTION

Let us focus now on the thermodynamics of the driven qutrit. In Fig. 5 we compare the experimental data for the average extracted work in the TPM scheme, $-\langle w \rangle_t^{\text{TPM}}$, with the unperturbed extracted work $W_{\text{ext}} = -\langle w \rangle_t$. In our experiment, the TPM scheme reduces the work extracted along the process. Comparing Fig. 5 and Fig. 4, we observe that peaks in the average work coincide with peaks in the negativity (nonclassical process). Moreover, Fig. 5 shows that the stochastic bound of Eq. (11) for work extraction is *violated*, showing that these peaks are high enough that they can *only* occur when q_{if} turns negative. The bound in Eq. (11) is a powerful tool for *witnessing* nonclassicality, as it relies only on the combination of the TPM statistics and END-time energy measurements.

A physical interpretation of the nonclassical work can be given by noting that, in our experiments, the negativity is concentrated in the anomalous excitation processes, whereby the negativity of the MHQ distribution is associated with the *largest* exciting transition, $w_{-+} = 2\Omega$ [Figs. 4(a)–4(c)].

FIG. 4. [(a)–(c)] Measured MHQs q_{if} as a function of time. The blue circles correspond to $f = -$, the orange squares to $f = 0$, and red triangles to $f = +$. The solid line represents the simulated data, while the dashed black line corresponds to $\sum_f |q_{if}|$. Note that only q_{-+} (c) exhibits negative values. (d) Experimental measurements (green circles) of the negativity [Eq. (3)] as a function of time (solid green line represents the simulated data). For almost all the interaction time t the negativity is larger than zero, hence overcoming the classical limit (dotted line) and entering into the nonclassical region (blue area). This region is bounded from above by $\sqrt{d} - 1$ (dashed line), where $d = 3$ is the dimension of the system's Hilbert space [17].

Classically, this transition contributes to the work absorbed, but quantumly (namely, by properly taking into account quantum coherence) it enhances the work extraction.

Let us further discuss this important aspect. The average work $\langle w \rangle_t$ [Eq. (4)] can be equivalently written as

$$\langle w \rangle_t = \sum_{i,f} \mu_{if} (1 + \aleph) \text{sgn}(q_{if}) w_{if}, \quad (20)$$

where we recall $w_{if} = E_f(t) - E_i(0)$, and the set of $\mu_{if} \equiv |q_{if}| / (1 + \aleph)$ forms a classical probability distribution. Moreover, \aleph is the negativity functional in Eq. (3) and $\text{sgn}(\cdot)$ is the sign function that is equal to +1 if (\cdot) is positive and -1 otherwise. Hence, by defining

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{E}_i(0) &\equiv (1 + \aleph) \text{sgn}(q_{if}) E_i(0) \\ \bar{E}_f(t) &\equiv (1 + \aleph) \text{sgn}(q_{if}) E_f(t), \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

we can interpret the average MHQ work $\langle w \rangle_t$ by means of a classical stochastic process defined by the set of probabilities

FIG. 5. Average unperturbed extracted work $W_{\text{ext}} = -\langle w \rangle_t = \sum_i p_i E_i(0) - \sum_f p_f^{\text{END}} E_f(t)$, and average extracted work in the TPM scheme, $-\langle w \rangle_t^{\text{TPM}} = -\sum_{i,f} p_{if}^{\text{TPM}} w_{if}$. The striped region on top (bottom) indicates violations of the stochastic work extraction (injection) bounds, achievable only if $\aleph \neq 0$ [see Eq. (11)].

$\{\mu_{if}\}$, i.e.,

$$\langle w \rangle_t = \sum_{i,f} \mu_{if} [\bar{E}_f(t) - \bar{E}_i(0)]. \quad (22)$$

One can thus compare Eq. (22) with the average TPM work $\langle w \rangle_t^{\text{TPM}}$ and then explain why nonclassicality (negativity of MHQs in our experimental case study) can entail a larger amount of extractable work. In fact, when negativity of the single term q_{if} is present, positive work terms $E_f(t) - E_i(0) \geq 0$ (corresponding to work done on the system in a classical picture) changes sign and they transform in $\bar{E}_f(t) - \bar{E}_i(0) < 0$, i.e., work that can be extracted. Moreover, always in case of negativity ($\aleph > 0$), the effective energies \bar{E} are obtained by multiplying E for $(1 + \aleph) > 1$. Hence, the contributions to the extractable work can be larger—in absolute value—than the corresponding positive work terms (done on the system) that enter the TPM work average, which decoheres the system with the first energy measurement. Figure 6 shows an instance of this key aspect by comparing the TPM and MHQ distributions at a time instant corresponding to one of the peaks of the negativity of MHQs in our experiment. All the negativity in the MHQ work distribution is associated

FIG. 6. Distributions q_{if} and p_{if}^{TPM} (p_{if} in labels to simplify notation) for each value of w_{if} at $t = 0.3 \mu\text{s}$, which is one of the times when the negativity functional \aleph is maximized. The values for $w_{if} = 0$ are not shown since they do not contribute to the work extraction.

with the largest exciting transition, $w_{-+} = 2\Omega$ that classically would contribute to the work done, but quantumly it enhances the work extraction. This negativity is destroyed by the TPM scheme, whose application thus results in a decreased work extraction.

Theoretical considerations often focus on the total negativity \aleph , but from a thermodynamic point of view, our experiments indicate that it is the *distribution of negativity* among the outcomes that plays a crucial role. In fact, numerical simulations (see Appendix) show that our experimental conditions are both close to minimizing q_{-+} as well as maximizing the work extraction.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

We presented the first experimental implementation of a wTPM scheme, which exploits error-cancellation techniques to reconstruct the Margenau-Hill quasiprobability associated to a quantum process. Specifically, the results of three distinct invasive protocols—involving strong (projective) measurements only—are linearly combined to infer the back-reaction-free limit.

The experiment was performed on an NV center in diamond driven by a microwave field acting as a work reservoir. Genuinely nonclassical energetics are witnessed using only projective measurements, without the need for ancillae or weak interactions. These features make the scheme ideally suited to probe nonclassical thermodynamics features in setups already analyzed with TPM schemes [67–69,73,74]. Using similar experimental resources as these experiments, we measured work extraction peaks associated to negativity peaks and in violation of a newly derived stochastic bound that, in itself, serves as a nonclassicality witness. These violations imply that such phenomenology cannot occur in TPM experiments. We gave a general interpretation of the nonclassical work phenomenon as an anomalous energy process, where negativity flips the conventional directionality of selected stochastic transitions, transforming contributions to work done into contributions to work extracted—leading to the observed peaks. In conclusion, we pave the way to quantum thermodynamic experiments exploiting error-cancellation techniques in a variety of platforms.

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APPENDIX: MAXIMIZING THE AMOUNT OF EXTRACTABLE WORK: NUMERICAL ANALYSIS FOR GENERIC PARAMETERS OF THE NV CENTER HAMILTONIAN

As described in the main text, the interaction between an NV center with an on-resonance microwave field results in the Hamiltonian, expressed in the MW rotating frame, provided by Eq. (18).

Here we aim to identify (i) the parameters for which q_{if} is minimized (for at least one set of i, f), (ii) the parameters for which the average MHQ extracted work $W_{\text{ext}} = -\langle w \rangle_t$ is maximized, and (iii) the parameters for which the negativity \aleph is maximized. Note that, a single set of parameters do not

FIG. 7. Results of the numerical simulations. In both panels (a) and (b), each empty blue circle represents the result for a set of random parameters of the system Hamiltonian and a random initial pure state. For each empty blue circle there are two orange crosses corresponding to the cases $\phi_1 = \phi_2 = \phi_1^R$ and $\phi_1 = \phi_2 = \phi_2^R$. Instead, the red circle with the error bars represents the experimentally measured values, as detailed in the main text. Finally, in panel (b), the horizontal line denotes the upper bound of the nonclassicality measure \aleph . Such a bound is equal to $\sqrt{d} - 1$, where $d = 3$ is the dimension of the Hilbert space of the system [17].

necessarily fulfill all the above conditions (i), (ii), and (iii). In order to achieve this, we run numerical simulations for 10000 different sets of random parameters $\{\Omega_1^R, \phi_1^R, \Omega_2^R, \phi_2^R\}$, such that $\{\Omega_1, \phi_1, \Omega_2, \phi_2\} = \{\Omega_1^R, \phi_1^R, \Omega_2^R, \phi_2^R\}$, and we calculate $\min[q_{if}]$, $\min[\langle w \rangle_t]$, and $\max[\aleph]$ for each set of parameters. The $\min[\cdot]$ and $\max[\cdot]$ are calculated over the time interval $t \in (0, 2\pi/\sqrt{2(\Omega_1^2 + \Omega_2^2) + \phi_1^2})$. The longest time value in this interval corresponds to a period of the dynamics in the case with $\phi_2 = \phi_1$. In addition, the considered random parameters correspond to random floating-point numbers in the intervals $\Omega_1^R \in [1, 20]$ MHz, $\phi_1^R \in [-2\Omega_1^R, 2\Omega_1^R]$, $\Omega_2^R \in [1, 20]$ MHz,

and $\phi_2^R \in [-2\Omega_2^R, 2\Omega_2^R]$. For each set of parameters, the initial state is a random pure state $\rho = |\xi\rangle\langle\xi|$, with $|\xi\rangle = ae^{i\phi_a}|+1\rangle + be^{i\phi_b}|0\rangle + \sqrt{1-a^2-b^2}|-1\rangle$, where a, b, ϕ_a, ϕ_b are random floating-point numbers in the intervals $[0, 1]$, $[0, \sqrt{1-a^2}]$, $[0, 2\pi)$, and $[0, 2\pi)$ respectively.

The results of the numerical simulations are summarized in Fig. 7. From these results it is evident that the condition $\phi_1 = \phi_2$ allows for the minimization of q_{if} , as well as the maximization of W_{ext} . In contrast, in order to maximize the negativity \aleph , it is more convenient to select the parameters of the system Hamiltonian such that $\phi_1 \neq \phi_2$.

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